

Critical data studies meets discard studies: Waste data reflectivity in digital urban waste tracking system

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Abstract

This article examines the implementation and impact of the Digital Urban Waste Tracking System (DUWTS) in Poland, a smart waste management technology designed to enhance waste segregation practices in urban environments. DUWTS combines public administration and private sector efforts to oversee proper waste disposal through advanced dataveillance technologies. The system utilizes electronic ground containers equipped with sensors and QR codes to weigh and record waste, aiming to improve recycling levels and manage waste data. The purpose of the research is to critically explore the concept of "waste data reflectivity," highlighting the socio-technological implications of data representation in waste management. The major findings reveal significant distortions and errors in data reflection, impacting various stakeholders, including municipalities, waste disposal companies, and residents. The study concludes that while DUWTS represents a technological advancement, it also perpetuates existing challenges in waste management by obscuring true complexities and responsibilities. Integrating critical discard studies and critical data studies, the article provides a nuanced understanding of the data-driven waste management systems' complexities and challenges.

Key words

digitalization, discard studies, waste data, data journey, critical data studies, data reflectivity, dataveillance, Digital Urban Waste Tracking System, smart waste management technology,

Introduction to the Digital Urban Waste Tracking System

In an era of digitalization and increasing ecological awareness, the waste management sector is transitioning towards leveraging advanced technologies. Today's world presents waste management as an increasingly complex and crucial challenge for urban environments. Concurrently, dataveillance technologies are emerging (Clarke, 1987; Pallitto, 2020).

Advocates of the 'smart city discourse regime' (Joss et al., 2018) propose optimizing recycling through artificial intelligence along with a set of interconnected data-centric and algorithmic technologies (Hoyng, 2023). These smart waste management technologies are being applied to transform waste into energy, manage smart containers, operate waste-sorting robots, develop waste generation models, and monitor and track waste (Frang et al., 2023). As demonstrated in this article, they also enable several 'socio-technical' functions, including individualizing responsibility for waste and the psychological surveillance and control of citizens' practices regarding waste segregation.

This article analyzes a smart waste management technology in Poland, referred to as the Digital Urban Waste Tracking System (DUWTS). DUWTS is designed to oversee and enforce proper waste segregation by monitoring citizens' waste segregation practices. It illustrates a collaboration between public administration and a private tech company. In this arrangement, municipalities act as clients who can purchase the system, while the private tech company develops and provides the technology. These public-private partnerships in municipal waste management represent a hybrid model where public and private interests are intertwined. This blend of the public and private sectors, facilitated by Big Brother-type technology, is gaining significance in the 21st century (Ash, 2013; Hoeyer, 2020).

The DUWTS has been deployed in eight small Polish cities, each with a population under 50,000 residents. It is specifically tailored for direct interaction with residents of multi-unit residential buildings, addressing the challenge of 'dispersion of responsibility leading to a relaxation of discipline' (Głuszyński et al., 2023: 20). This issue results in 'low quality of selective waste collection in multi-family housing' (Deloitte Advisory, 2020: 24). To tackle this problem, the creators of DUWTS assert that their technology offers a viable solution. A key component of this solution is electronic ground containers that weigh and record waste, providing detailed information about the type and quantity of waste generated by households. The data collected by these containers form the foundation for a data-driven approach, setting the stage for the process of 'waste data reflectivity' that I will define in the next section.

Waste data reflectivity in smart waste management systems

In contemporary times, the traditional concept of waste is evolving into a domain governed by data and machine learning algorithms (Frang et al., 2023). Globally, especially in regions experimenting with smart city concepts, waste is no longer perceived merely as a physical substance. Instead, it undergoes datafication, a process that transforms its physical form into digital data. This 'innovative' form of knowledge production converts 'old'

information into pure data points, which can then be reused to gain new insights (Flyverbom & Murray, 2018; Kitchin, 2014; Ruppert et al., 2017). The idea of smart cities, which redefines waste through datafication, signifies a shift from tangible trash to data and algorithms.

This transformation suggests a broader adoption of technologies for citizen data collection and processing (Walentek, 2021; Bibri and Krogstie, 2020). Waste management technology generates 'waste data,' quantifying information about waste production, management, and recycling patterns¹. This process is significant, as waste data illuminates the magnitudes and complexities of global waste challenges, presenting a concerning scenario of the world's growing waste crisis².

Understanding how waste becomes information is crucial for grasping its full impact on urban planning, environmental policy, and sustainability practices.

The DUWTS exemplifies a transformation in waste management, shifting from conventional methods to a sophisticated data-driven approach. DUWTS employs three key techniques used in waste management systems for smart cities:

- Identification Techniques: Radio frequency identification (RFID) tags and barcodes enable efficient waste tracking and monitoring.
- Data Acquisition Technology: Sensors and imaging provide valuable data on waste generation and composition, enabling better waste management decisions.
- Data Communications Technology: Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and global mobile communication systems facilitate communication and data transfer between waste management systems and stakeholders (Frang et al., 2023).

All these techniques are integral to the flow of waste data within the DUWTS system, leading to a phenomenon I define in this article as data reflectivity.

Data reflectivity serves as the central conceptual framework in this article. This concept refers to the capacity of data or information to accurately represent and mirror real-world phenomena or entities in the virtual realm. The notion of data reflectivity has evolved within discussions on data quality and its ability to depict reality across fields such as data science, data analysis, machine learning, and artificial intelligence. The primary challenge in data

¹ For a comprehensive collection of data on global waste patterns, see the online repository provided by Statista at: Global Waste Generation – Statistics & Facts, Access: Aug, 31. 2023.

² If our current trajectory persists, global waste production will skyrocket, reaching levels 73% higher than 2020 by the year 2050 (World Bank, 2021). Each year, a staggering 2.01 billion tons of municipal solid waste are produced worldwide (Filipenco, 2023). Within the European Union alone, 595 million tons of municipal waste are generated annually, making up 27% of the EU's total 2.2 billion tonnes of waste. Furthermore, waste data reveals that countries such as Austria, Luxembourg, Denmark, Belgium, and Germany lead the EU in municipal waste production (European Parliament, 2023).

reflectivity is how effectively data reflects the underlying reality or truth about a subject. High data reflectivity means that the data provides an accurate representation of the actual state or characteristics being observed, enabling conclusions that closely approximate reality. Conversely, low data reflectivity indicates that the data is incomplete, heavily distorted, or significantly deviates from the real-world situation. In the case of DUWTS, I adapt this general concept of data reflectivity and reframe it as 'waste data reflectivity.'

Critical perspective on waste data reflectivity in DUWTS

The central inquiry of this article focuses on how waste data are reflected through the DUWTS and explores the implications of data reflectivity in this advanced technology. In this context, 'data reflectivity' refers to the capability of accurately representing and mirroring the reality of waste as 'waste data' collected through DUWTS. The investigation delves into the methods by which waste data are reflected back to diverse stakeholders, including individual residents, municipalities, and waste disposal companies. The concept of 'data reflectivity' is pivotal, encompassing the processes of how data are defined, collected, processed, and ultimately reflected back to users. It is important to note, however, that the way in which data is reflected is not neutral, echoing the sentiment that Big Data cannot be a neutral tool (Dalton and Thatcher, 2014). Dietmar Offenhuber (2017) also notes that all readings and representations of the waste system are necessarily incomplete and influenced by specific goals and interests. Moreover, the infrastructures that process our waste often remain opaque. Due to the non-neutral nature of data reflection, this article critically examines the implications of non-neutral data reflectivity within the DUWTS.

To thoroughly examine this non-neutrality, the article poses a series of research questions that aim to dissect various aspects of waste data management within the context of the DUWTS. These questions are essential for understanding the dynamic interplay between technology, data interpretation, and stakeholder interests.

- How does the DUWTS system reflect waste data?
- How effectively are waste data reflected in the DUWTS?
- What errors and noise occur in the process of data reflectivity?
- For what purposes are waste data reflected back to individual residents, municipalities, and waste management companies?
- What are the socio-technological consequences of waste data reflection?

In exploring these questions, this study delves into the intricacies of Smart Waste Management Technology, as exemplified by the DUWTS, to uncover the nuanced interplay between data

reflectivity and its broader implications. The literature seldom explores how waste data are reflected or the socio-technological consequences of such data reflectivity. Aiming to fill this gap, this article poses research questions that propel us into a critical examination of the future of Smart Waste Management Technologies and their complex societal repercussions.

House of mirrors: Distortions in waste data reflectivity

This discussion will illustrate how the DUWTS, much like a house of mirrors, employs various mechanisms of data reflectivity that distort our perceptions of waste. In this paper, I argue that the Digital Urban Waste Tracking System functions similarly to a 'house of mirrors,' featuring at least three types of distorting mirrors. Just as fun house mirrors distort the reflection of a person, making them appear tall and thin in one mirror and short and fat in another, DUWTS distorts the reality of waste data reflectivity.

The analogical mechanisms presented in DUWTS mirrors significantly alter the reality of waste data by warping it. Below, in Table 1, I present three types of mirrors found within DUWTS. Each corresponds to different stakeholders and produces distinct effects on the accuracy and perception of waste data reflectivity.

Stakeholders	Type of mirror	Illuso consequences of data distortion	Strategies/technologies of (un)knowing
1. Municipality	Concave mirror: Illusion of size	Control over the collected data about recycling levels	Dataveillance
2. Waste disposal companies	Kaleidoscopic mirror: Multiple reflections	Implementation of dynamic waste collection	Data-driven optimization
3. Residents	Ceiling mirror: Inverted space	Implementation of pay-as-you-throw method	Data-based individualization

Table 1. Data Reflectivity Mirrors in DUWTS and Their Effects

In Table 1, the first column lists the stakeholders who examine the data reflections. The second column includes mirrors such as the Concave Mirror, Kaleidoscopic Mirror, and Ceiling Mirrors, which metaphorically represent how data reflectivity is distorted. The third column describes the illusory consequences of these distortions: control over recycling data, dynamic waste collection, and the pay-as-you-throw method. The fourth column outlines the strategies and technologies of (un)knowing, which influence how data is managed and perceived.

The process of deformation through data reflectivity is labeled using the concept of technologies of (un)knowing, as conceptualized by Alexander and O'Hare (2020). Based on my analysis of 'smart' waste segregation bins, I identify three types of technologies of (un)knowing rooted in critical data studies: dataveillance, data-driven optimization, and data-based individualization. These strategies influence how data is managed and perceived in waste management systems like DUWTS, concealing or distorting certain aspects of reality.

This article critiques the portrayal of data-based technologies for waste management as modern environmental solutions. While some literature hails data-based technologies as innovative approaches to knowledge creation (Flyverbom & Murray, 2018; Kitchin, 2014; Ruppert et al., 2017), this techno-optimistic perspective must be challenged. Data-driven technologies often act as 'technologies of (un)knowing'. In the case of the Digital Urban Waste Tracking System, these technologies obscure the problem of excess disposable packaging, inadvertently shielding tech companies' vested interests and presenting them as public benefits (Alexander & O'Hare, 2020).

The table reveals three strategies of technologies of (un)knowing, associated stakeholders, and the illusory consequences of distorted reflections through the mirrors. As argued in the results section, these actions obscure real issues in municipal waste management and have broader socio-cultural and economic implications, mirroring societal challenges in the digital era. Analyzing this technology within the presented framework demonstrates that it is more than just a technological advancement in waste management; it leads to a deeper understanding of the role of data in waste management. The non-neutral nature of data reflection can lead to biased decision-making and inadequate policy responses. Therefore, focusing on understanding the complexities of the DUWTS is crucial for better informing waste policy formulation and decision-making about waste segregation practices.

Integrating critical discard studies and critical data studies: A new approach in waste management research

In this article, I synthesize two interconnected fields of study: the interdisciplinary domain of critical discard studies (Liboiron and Lepawsky, 2022; Drackner 2005) and the burgeoning field of critical data studies (Gitelman and Jackson, 2013; Iliadis and Russo, 2016). Critical discard studies, a multifaceted subfield of critical theory and interdisciplinary research that examines waste and wasting from social, cultural, economic, philosophical and political perspectives, prompt us to perceive waste not merely in functional terms, enriching our understanding of waste's societal role. This approach aligns with related disciplines such as

rubbish theory (Thompson, 2017), waste studies (Gille and Lepawsky, 2021), garbology (Sztangret and Reformat, 2020) and notably, the anthropology of waste (Eriksen and Schober, 2017; Schlehe and Yulianto, 2019), which applies a cultural perspective to the dynamics of power, class, religion, materiality, and economics. Influential figures like Alexander and Reno (2012, 2014) have broadened our comprehension of waste, underscoring global recycling industry trends and waste's productive afterlife, positioning it as a pivotal lens for examining modernity, materialism, and our interaction with the non-human world in the Anthropocene.

Moreover, critical data studies scrutinize the cultural, ethical, and intricate complexities inherent in Big Data, and also examine the ways in which data is produced, circulated, and consumed within broader socio-technical systems and power structures. By challenging the perception of Big Data as an unbiased and neutral entity, this field of study emphasizes the necessity of placing it within a broader context that includes humans, objects, and ideas. It seeks to reveal the extent to which established data structures influence societal norms and the minutiae of everyday life, critically assessing the cultural, political, and societal impact of data (Iliadis and Russo, 2016). Critical data studies explore Big Data from specific angles, such as its role in surveillance (Crampton et al., 2014), and strive to determine who exactly commands control over Big Data, who orchestrates its creation and analysis, and what driving forces underpin their endeavors (Thatcher, 2014). These studies also shed light on the mythological foundations of Big Data, exposing it as a product of a technological ethos that places unwavering faith in quantification and its potential to mirror reality's intricacies (Boyd and Crawford, 2012). As Dalton, Taylor, and Thatcher (2014) assert, the myths surrounding Big Data are deeply ingrained in contemporary society, influencing concepts from the quantified self to the idea of smart cities.

The exploration of waste data in this article advocates for a melding of critical discard studies with critical data studies—a conjunction infrequently addressed in scholarly texts. Social science research often neglects the technological components of waste management, including the adoption of digital technologies and their social and cultural consequences. Moreover, there is a pronounced absence of the waste data concept within traditional discard studies. Academic discussions on the technological dimensions of waste management, particularly those involving waste data and smart city frameworks, are conspicuously lacking. Waste management datasets, especially those pertinent to fraud detection, are typically the purview of data science, as Hewiagh et al.'s research (2021) illustrates. Yet, there is a stark gap in the socio-cultural and critical examination of the digital surveillance technologies in waste management, resulting in a piecemeal grasp of their function in oversight and control. The

scholarly analysis often fails to consider how these technologies, designed for the oversight and enforcement of recycling, impact society at large.

Only Dietmar Offenhuber (2017) has extensively written on waste and data. His book "Waste is Information: Infrastructural Legibility and Governance" is literature situated at the intersection of discard studies and data studies. The book explores the idea that waste and waste systems are not just technical or environmental problems. Offenhuber discusses waste as a source of information, highlighting that waste data can reveal important insights about the operation and management of cities, focusing on the processes by which waste is classified, monitored, and managed. Waste data informs city policies and waste management practices. Offenhuber suggests that a better understanding and use of waste data can contribute to more effective and equitable urban environmental management. However, the book lacks a clear critical element. The primary issue it recognizes is that 'insufficient data generates problems in the context of waste management,' meaning that waste data is inaccurate, insufficient, or too general, leading to a lack of accountability, which can obscure pollution sources and cloak questionable practices (Offenhuber, 2017: 4).

However, the literature on waste data lacks an example that shows that the mere generation of data by technology can obscure actual pollution sources, shifting responsibility to an entity not responsible for waste production. Hence, I provide the DUWTS as an example of how waste data can obscure rather than reveal vital information about waste management in the context of municipal and national policy.

This article aims to fill the gaps in the current literature by focusing on the own concept of 'data reflectivity.' It goes beyond the direct interactions between humans and waste to explore 'data reflectivity'—the complex dynamics between individuals and waste as mediated by modern technological data. Although the anthropology of waste has significantly enriched our understanding of the interactions between humans and waste, it has yet to thoroughly address the complexities introduced by recent technological advancements. This article delves into these neglected areas, highlighting how digital technology intersects with waste management practices and the broad societal implications that ensue.

Data journey as a methodological approach

In this article, I employ a data journey methodology, rooted in critical data studies, to unpack the 'life of data' (Beer and Burrows, 2013; Ruppert et al., 2012; as cited by Bates et al., 2016). This approach illuminates data's life as it travels between and through the sites of data production, processing, distribution, and usage. The data journey methodology focuses on the

life of data as it moves through space and time, across different places and cultures of usage. It traverses the 'information production chain' (Braman, 2006) from initial production to re-use in diverse contexts. This methodology opposes a deeply reductionist and technocentric approach to data, advocating for a 'situated, reflective, and contextually nuanced epistemology' (Kitchin, 2014; as cited by Bates et al., 2016). It demonstrates that data are not objective but are shaped and interpreted—they are 'cooked' (Gitelman and Jackson, 2013) and 'made' (Vis, 2013; as cited by Bates et al., 2016).

In this article, the data journey methodology was utilized to trace the trajectory of waste data, incorporating ethnographic techniques such as desk study, in-depth interviews and participant observation. This methodology allows for the tracking of the data lifecycle from its source, through various stages of processing and utilization. Additionally, it enables ethnography, which allows for observation of this process in real social and cultural contexts, providing rich information on practices, interactions, and meanings associated with the data. Combining ethnographic research with the data journey method focuses on a deeper understanding of the social and cultural context in which data is generated, processed, and utilized. This is done by taking into account the perspectives of various stakeholders involved in this process. Ethnography, through direct observations and interviews, enriches the data journey analysis by revealing hidden assumptions, values, meanings, interactions, and practices related to the data lifecycle. The integration of these two methods can help identify challenges and issues such as privacy concerns, ethical matters, and inequalities in data access.

The methodological approach termed 'data journey' in the context of waste data within the DUWTS was connected with following ethnographic techniques:

At the national level:

- Conducted field observations (participant observation) while attending a municipal waste management conference in 2023. During this event, I observed Polish experts engaging in discussions and presentations.
- Conducted three interviews (in-depth interviews) with experts in the field of waste management in Poland. In the article, they are referred to as the creators, experts, or specialists responsible for implementing this technology.

At the municipal level:

- Observed six DUWTS locations in two different cities.
- Conducted eight interviews with municipal employees at the Waste Management Departments in the municipal offices.

- Held spontaneous conversations with five residents living in DUWTS area (users of technology).

At the DUWTS manufacturer level:

- Conducted a two-day observation of a private technology company where DUWTS is designed.
- Conducted four interviews with employees of the private technology company involved in the development of this technology as part of their professional responsibilities.

Specific details that could lead to their identification, as well as the technology itself, have been anonymized. The interviews were transcribed, and quotes were translated from Polish to English. The information included in the article pertains to what is available online about such technologies or falls under public information access. All interviewees provided consent for their participation and the use of their statements in the research. The data collected during the research were further secured using anonymizing techniques for documents, and then analyzed using MaxQDA software. This careful approach ensured the confidentiality of the participants and the integrity of the research process. The diagram outlined in the summary was created using MAXQDA's smart coding tool, which helped visualize the relationships among the codes embedded within the material.

Context of waste data in DUWTS in polish waste system

This section justifies selecting Poland as the location for this research and demonstrates why Poland is a critical site for studying waste data reflectivity relative to the rest of the EU. In discussing the Polish municipal waste management system within the context of the DUWTS dataveillance technology, I take into account Offenhuber's observation (2017: 28) that 'all readings and representations of the waste system are necessarily incomplete and based on a particular goal and interest.' Acknowledging the inherent constraints of my analysis, I have deliberately chosen to focus on specific aspects of waste data reflection within the Polish waste system. This targeted approach is illustrated in Figure 1, which depicts the role of smart containers in the DUWTS system and their positioning within the context of municipal waste data in Poland.

Figure 1: Data reflectivity in Digital Urban Waste Tracking System within the Polish waste system

As depicted in Figure 1, the data reflectivity process in waste system begins with EU recycling level policy and traverses vertically across various levels, from government policy to municipalities, ultimately placing the onus of recycling on the citizens. As Offenhuber (2017:....) notes, 'the waste system as an analytical object shares many representational, phenomenological, and ontological challenges with other kinds of systems'. Consequently, the Polish waste system is interconnected with other systems – including the European Union, national governance, local municipalities, and individual households.

Poland presents a unique case for the study of smart waste management technology like DUWTS, due to its distinctive challenges within the European Union's waste management framework. At a municipal waste management conference, Polish experts unanimously recognized the EU as the primary authority in creating municipal waste recycling regulations. Among these, Directive (EU) 2018/851 (Article 11) stands as a key legislative piece that mandates a 55% recycling or reuse rate for all municipal waste by 2025, with targets increasing to 60% by 2030 and 65% by 2035 (European Parliament, 2023). Each EU member state is

required to consistently meet these targets. This directive is crucial for holding member states accountable, imposing significant financial penalties for non-compliance. The recycling levels established by the EU have become a fundamental reference for the creation of surveillance practices in municipal waste management across EU countries. These standards also provide the main justification for developing the DUWTS surveillance technology, which originated in Poland—a country where recycling levels are exceptionally low and significantly below the EU's target³.

Another aspect observed at a municipal waste management conference was that Polish experts emphasized the need for action at the government policy level to meet EU requirements under Directive (EU) 2018/851, particularly by Poland's Ministry of Climate and Environment, which is tasked with guiding the development of environmental policies and legal frameworks. The Ministry should have already taken specific action involving the implementation of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), which mandates producers to create more recyclable packaging. The implementation deadline passed in January 2023 (RP 2024), yet EPR has not yet been implemented in Poland (Portal Komunalny 2021). EPR is the missing link for the entire industry in the management of packaging waste. Introducing EPR would align with EU standards and address the significant gap between municipal recycling rates and EU targets. This policy gap highlights the challenges that local authorities face in adhering to EU waste policies. Despite numerous suggestions from the entire Polish municipal waste sector, EPR has yet to be implemented by the Ministry⁴.

As an EU member state, Poland is subject to stringent EU regulations, yet it continues to record one of the lowest recycling rates in Europe and has not implemented Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR). This significant gap between Polish waste management practices and EU directives is key to understanding why a technology like DUWTS emerged in Poland rather than elsewhere. In this context, DUWTS exploits the absence of EPR and low recycling levels, offering a 'smart' technological solution intended to bridge these policy implementation gaps. However, this tech-centric approach risks neglecting essential aspects of

³ Data from 2018 (López-Portillo et al., 2021) reveal that Poland belongs to the cluster of European countries with the lowest average recycling rate, at 29.97%. Furthermore, as demonstrated by data presented by Eurostat (2023), in 2022, Poland's 'Recycling Rate of Municipal Waste' was 40.3%, compared to the European average of 48.7%. Poland was ranked 24th among 38 European countries (Eurostat, 2023). This positions Poland at a higher risk of incurring financial penalties from the EU for not meeting the stipulated recycling targets. For example, it is projected that in 2024, Poland will pay approximately 2.3 billion PLN in plastic tax for unprocessed plastic (Polska Agencja Prasowa, 2024).

⁴ At the beginning of 2024, the European Commission initiated legal proceedings against Poland for failing to properly transpose regulations concerning the EPR system (Portal Samorządowy 2024).

policy alignment and efficient waste management strategies. It simplifies the complexities of waste management by portraying technology as a universal solution, potentially overshadowing the need for comprehensive policy reforms. This strategy exemplifies the 'Technologies of (Un)Knowing' concept (Alexander, O'Hare, 2020), which hidden complexities and the dangers of relying solely on technological solutions for waste management. Having explored the primary context of waste data reflectivity in Poland's waste management system, our discussion now shifts to the datafication process within DUWTS.

In the unique context of Poland, characterized by coordination issues between Ministry actions and EU directives, the DUWTS emerges as a 'innovative' technology on both a Polish and European scale.

The initial step in DUWTS data journey: Datafication of waste through QR codes

In this section I deep dive into the datafication process of waste data within DUWTS, exploring how waste datafication occurs and critical assessing its effectiveness.

In the DUWTS, QR codes are fundamental elements of infrastructure that initiate the data reflectivity journey. Each enrolled household is provided with special QR code stickers for waste disposal. These stickers, intended for single use, come in various colors such as yellow, blue, green, brown, or black, corresponding to different waste fractions. Users affix the appropriate sticker to their trash bag, scan it at the QR code reader on the corresponding smart container, and activate a mechanism that opens the device's flap, allowing for the disposal of waste. Upon disposal, the system automatically records the weight of the bag, for example, as 0.5 kg.

A local controller, which oversees the display, QR reader, and scale, manages this information. It forwards the data to another controller tasked with data consolidation. These data are subsequently transmitted to the central system at regular intervals, such as every 15 minutes, and are associated with the individual resident's account within DUWTS.

QR codes, when used in conjunction with readers, create what Gabriela de Seta (2021) describes as an 'infrastructural gate.' Through this gate, physical waste is transformed into digital data, thereby facilitating the flow of information. These codes act not only as keys to various segments of the system but also directly link residents' actions to the data-collecting system, thus integrating daily waste disposal activities with sophisticated data management processes.

Waste management technologies such as DUWTS 'theoretically' eliminate anonymity. With residents using QR codes on trash bags, accurate 'identification of the origin of each trash bag' and verification of the identities of those disposing of waste in multi-unit buildings become possible. This, in turn, enforces proper segregation and allows tracking of who is disposing of what waste. As noted by a technology company employee, QR codes are 'the resident's signature on their waste'. In a world where every interaction with technology is recorded and analyzed, scanning a QR code becomes not only an action within waste management but also a record of residents' activities. Considering the data collected by DUWTS as digital traces, as discussed by Nanna Bonde Thylstrup (2019) in 'Data Out of Place,' the system fosters a culture of identifiability within the context of urban waste. The DUWTS includes identification techniques such as barcodes, which enable effective waste tracking and monitoring (Frang et al., 2023). We likely live in a new culture of identifiability where technology collect and disseminate subject traces, utilizing machine learning processes (Chun, 2016b).

This culture of traceability is further supported by cameras mounted around DUWTS containers. An advanced visual monitoring system played a critical role in overseeing the accuracy of data collection in the DUWTS. Equipped with cameras and LED lamps with proximity sensors, this system exist to ensure effective verification of events around waste containers. Cameras operating in monochromatic mode at night have a wide range, reaching up to 25 meters, and a viewing angle of 103 degrees, allowing observation of key areas around the containers. In the case of a single row of containers, at least two cameras are always installed. This monitoring system was created to identifies illegal dumping of waste and intrusions into the container area. Footage transmitted directly to the central monitoring system. Visual monitoring also serves a preventive and disciplining function. It is supposed to influence residents' behavior and increasing their self-discipline, deters improper actions. The system generates notifications in case of detected irregularities, which can be transmitted to relevant supervisory services.

Photography 1. Bulky waste near DUWTS containers

A critical examination of the veracity of the datafied waste data is necessary at the start of the multifaceted data journey within the DUWTS. QR-coded bags are intended to ensure the accuracy of data reflection within DUWTS, facilitating not only the tracking and verification of waste segregation but also the assignment of specific waste to particular households. However, it is uncertain if they actually achieve this. Residents admitted during our investigation that neither they nor their neighbors segregated waste accurately. Furthermore, they often dispose of their waste in conventional bins adjacent to each other inside residential areas. Sometimes, they do not attach QR codes to the bags but only use them to open the containers, which complicates the clear assignment of waste to a specific user. Consequently, QR code-generated data does not accurately reflect the actual mass of waste generated by residents. In practice, the datafication process at DUWTS merely captures what residents claim they have in their trash bags⁵.

⁵ To verify the authenticity of the data, physical inspections are necessary. Such inspections are sporadically conducted by municipal employees. They are performed manually—municipal workers open the containers, inspect specific waste bags, and take photographs. Due to the small number of staff dedicated to these inspections, they are infrequent. As a result, it sometimes happens that even three-quarters of the households inspected receive a negative outcome from the audit.

The system is susceptible to various types of deception when it comes to the datafication of waste. Municipal employees have noted, "This system can be deceived in many ways. If someone wants to cheat the system, they are free to do so." The legibility of these data is therefore minimal, as understood in the context of Offenhuber (2017). Despite numerous sensors inside the DUWTS containers and a complex data flow system, the readability and reliability of the data remain questionable. Ethnographic field observations further revealed that many bulky waste items were left near containers despite the smart monitoring systems designed to prevent this (Photography 1). There is no information about these abandoned waste items within DUWTS, highlighting a significant gap in the data.

The high level of distortion in data reflectivity is evident from the very beginning of the data journey in DUWTS. This distortion undermines the system's ability to provide accurate and actionable waste management data, calling into question the overall effectiveness and reliability of the DUWTS in its current form.

The visible elements of the DUWTS infrastructure, such as QR codes and monitoring, create an impression of supervision, represents a modern surveillance structure. DUWTS technology has been designed to ensure that its surveillance is visible (Offenhuber 2017: 29). This visibility of surveillance aims to foster self-discipline among residents. Even municipal employees admit that this technology is intended to psychologically pressure residents into correctly sorting their waste. However, DUWTS is ultimately ineffective in properly tracking and managing waste data, as the technological surveillance is merely illusory. The system only records the declared waste, not the actual contents of the bags.

The second step in DUWTS data journey: The central System

This section explores the pivotal role of the DUWTS Central System, essential for integrating and centralizing a comprehensive array of waste management data. In this process, technology transmits data from residents to the central system. The Central System, housed on the private servers of the technology company responsible for developing DUWTS, acts as a central hub where waste data from containers are processed and stored. It serves as a repository for resident waste data, embodying the integration of diverse data streams into a unified system. This consolidation of information is succinctly captured by an interviewee's observation: "Everything goes into one bag in the central system."

The system offers comprehensive access to data for each apartment connected to DUWTS, displayed through a virtual map. This map shows the locations of all containers across Poland and provides the addresses of the apartments, along with access to detailed data about

them and aggregate location statistics at the level of neighborhoods, municipalities, and the entire country. Moreover, the DUWTS Central System includes live video recordings from cameras placed around waste containers, enabling real-time monitoring of the vicinity. This capability is enhanced by a playback feature that allows for the retrospective review of archived events by date and time, thereby bolstering control over waste segregation and data collection processes.

Employees of the private company, with the necessary authorizations, can visualize and manage waste data on a national scale through the central system, which can be interpreted as an 'all-seeing eye,' symbolizing pervasive surveillance (Lyon 2014). This metaphor emphasizes the system's complete visibility and the absence of anonymity, as highlighted by statements from employees regarding the transparency and control it offers. One employee explicitly stated, 'There's no anonymity here, and I know exactly what everyone is doing,' while another added, 'We see everything.' These remarks highlight the system's extensive control capabilities.

Waste data collected in the central DUWTS system are subsequently processed and filtered to suit the specific needs of various stakeholders. This information is tailored for different users and transmitted to corresponding subsystems. Through dedicated apps, waste data are reflected back to stakeholders, including residents themselves. There are specialized applications for municipal employees, waste disposal companies, and residents, each featuring interfaces that display data differently. These app interfaces act as filters, aligning with Paul Kockelman's (2013) 'sieve' concept. The technology company determines the presentation and accessibility of data at the design stage of the system. Access to data varies according to user permissions, ensuring that each user only views information relevant to their role within the system. This data profiling process introduces a controlled access to waste information (Hoyn, 2023). Consequently, DUWTS generates diverse 'reflections' of waste data, customized to the needs of different users from municipalities to waste collection companies to residents.

The third step in DUWTS data journey: Data reflection via application

In the third step of the DUWTS data journey, I delve into the intricate process of data reflection via application, utilizing distinct 'mirrors' to illustrate various aspects of waste data presentation. These metaphorical mirrors help explain how data is tailored for different stakeholders—municipalities, waste disposal companies, and residents—through customized applications. Each mirror—Concave, Kaleidoscopic, and Ceiling—uniquely influences the perception and handling of data, highlighting the nuanced interaction between the central system and its users. These reflections are not mere replications; they are shaped by the specific

needs and roles of each group, significantly affecting their understanding and actions concerning waste management. Each type of data reflection in the DUWTS application does not present data holistically but offers a different representation of waste systems, designed for a specific purpose and tailored to particular interests (Offenhuber, 2017). This section will explore the role of each mirror in detail.

Concave mirror: Data reflection to municipalities

In this section of the article, I explore how residents' waste data are reflected in the municipality app, marking the beginning of our examination into the first mirror of data reflectivity within the DUWTS. This investigation reveals the non-neutral nature of data reflectivity within the system. The "Concave Mirror" metaphor, crafted to depict the distortion of data transmitted from the DUWTS Central System to municipalities, illustrates how data about residents' waste management can be exaggerated, creating an illusion of size. This metaphor draws from the properties of concave mirrors, which magnify images and produce an exaggerated effect. Within the DUWTS context, this metaphor aptly symbolizes how the system can skew waste data, artificially boosting perceived recycling levels and fostering a misleading impression of municipal effectiveness in waste management.

The municipal app, a core component of the DUWTS, provides municipalities with a view that reflects the central system's data. A representative from the private-tech company highlighted the comprehensive range of information available to municipalities via the app:

Municipalities are granted full access to an extensive range of information. Individual accounts are created for municipal office employees who can log in via a web browser or directly to their accounts. This unified system provides a comprehensive view for all users within the municipality. It also includes a virtual map showing all the container locations in the city, the status of devices, availability, the mass of waste in each module, and the level of fill, among other detailed data points.

While the DUWTS application designed for municipalities contains numerous data points, features, and capabilities, it constitutes a specific representation of waste systems created for a particular purpose. This representation focuses on recycling levels, as discussed in the section 'Context of waste data in DUWTS in the Polish waste system.' In the application designed for municipalities, the data reflection view has been crafted to suggest the potentially achievable recycling levels. In DUWTS these levels are calculated based on data declared via QR codes (which, as noted in the initial step of the data journey, are themselves inadequate). However, this data shows the segregation statistics achieved by residents. While segregation statistics are entirely different from recycling levels, the municipal application uses this data to suggest the levels being achieved.

The suggested recycling levels view in the municipality app supports the official narrative of the private-tech company, asserting that the DUWTS system enables municipalities to control and manage data related to achieving recycling levels from Directive EU 2018/851. The developers of DUWTS leverage this scenario by presenting their technology as crucial for municipalities, claiming it helps meet stringent EU recycling targets and potentially reduces financial penalties. A DUWTS company representative warned:

The system, which monitors and controls every kilogram of waste produced by residents, is primarily dedicated to local government units, as cities must achieve appropriate recycling levels year after year. This year it is 35%, next year it will be 45%, and so on. Unfortunately, some municipalities approach these looming threats too nonchalantly. They claim there is still time, but there isn't, because these levels are already very high this year.

The narrative that municipalities can achieve recycling levels thanks to DUWTS is driven by the company's official communication channels. On social media, the company describes DUWTS as "a modern tool that not only increases the effectiveness of segregation but also contributes to the enhancement of recycling levels," and "the most effective tool for achieving the required recycling levels by municipalities." However, the reality of achieving these recycling levels is significantly more complex and fraught with challenges than the optimistic company narrative suggests.

In the municipality app, the data reflectivity of meeting recycling levels is manipulated, creating an illusion around these levels. Data reflectivity in the app is distorted for two main reasons:

Firstly, the actual recyclability of waste in Poland is influenced by numerous factors beyond DUWTS technological capabilities. Recycling levels involve not just the amount of waste segregated by residents but also determining how much of this waste is recyclable, processed, and sold as raw material. This is linked to the quality of waste and the capacity of recycling facilities, which are often inadequate. An expert highlighted the disparity between what residents sort and what is genuinely recyclable:

What residents segregate is not necessarily what is recyclable because a large portion of packaging that enters the Polish market is simply not suitable for recycling. Less than half of what's in the yellow bags is recyclable. Despite the effort involved in segregating waste, a significant portion ends up in landfills or incinerators due to flaws in Poland's Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) system.

Secondly, the effectiveness of the DUWTS system is limited due to its small scale. Even if DUWTS had an impact on recycling levels, it is too minimal to register. Municipalities do not

observe an increase in recycling levels because the system's reach is limited. DUWTS covers only a small number of households, making its impact on city-wide recycling imperceptible. A municipal employee described this limitation:

At the end of March, we prepare a report on the amount of waste collected and recycling levels to the marshal. Currently, we have 700 households covered by DUWTS technology, which is too little on a city-wide scale to make a difference. We have the same recycling levels as before, so no fines for now. The system's scale is too small to discuss recycling levels meaningfully.

This overestimation by illusion of size serves a deeper purpose: it masks the inadequacies in actual waste segregation and recycling, providing a semblance of efficiency and compliance with EU standards that is often not present in reality. The company's overestimation of the system's capabilities not only creates a facade of efficiency but also leads to significant socio-technological consequences. It fosters a false sense of compliance with EU standards, potentially resulting in non-compliance penalties and contributing to a misinformed public perception about the effectiveness of municipal recycling programs. This mirror reflecting data misalignment with reality provokes a focus on the initial stages of waste handling rather than the complete recycling process. The process remains opaque for the waste beyond the DUWTS infrastructure (Offenhuber, 2017).

The reflectivity of data in the DUWTS app serves as a sophisticated form of "dataveillance," where skewed reflections are not merely errors but strategic technologies of ignorance and concealment. By projecting a distorted reality, the system obscures the complex relationships and challenges inherent in sustainable waste management, misleading stakeholders about the efficacy of their recycling efforts. This is achieved through continuous monitoring and tracking of residents' waste data, creating a form of data surveillance that collects detailed information on how and when waste is generated and managed. The DUWTS app for municipalities is deeply rooted in these dataveillance mechanisms, which underpin the understanding of waste management's evolution in the digital age. Dataveillance represents evolving forms of surveillance and infrastructural power, encapsulating the idea of pervasive digital oversight, as discussed by David Lyon (2014), and aligning with the concepts of the 'quantified self' and the 'sensor society' (van Dijck, 2014).

In conclusion, the "Concave Mirror" metaphor within the DUWTS framework not only highlights the distortions in data reflection but also emphasizes the broader implications of such distortions in modern waste management. While the system is promoted as a tool for advancing urban efficiency and aligning with smart city concepts, it ultimately complicates the genuine

assessment and improvement of municipal recycling practices. This discrepancy between the system's promises and its actual performance illustrates the challenges facing municipalities striving to meet recycling standards, revealing the essential gaps between technological potential and practical reality in environmental sustainability efforts.

Kaleidoscopic mirror: Data reflection to waste disposal companies

In investigating the DUWTS' second mirror of data reflectivity, I explore how residents' waste data are mirrored in the application designed for waste disposal companies. This app serves as the primary element of the data reflectivity infrastructure, facilitating seamless exchanges between the DUWTS Central System and the waste disposal companies' app. This system creates a kaleidoscopic effect, reflecting the data in multiple ways and producing an exaggerated perception of the waste management process's effectiveness. The "Kaleidoscopic Mirror" metaphor aptly depicts the distortion of data transmitted from the DUWTS Central System to waste disposal companies, symbolizing how the system can skew waste data, creating an artificial multiplicity and fostering a misleading illusion of the companies' efficiency. The concept of dynamic waste collection is central to this mirror, demonstrating the accuracy of data reflectivity in the waste disposal companies' app.

The DUWTS provides real-time information on the fill levels of containers, the weight of the waste, and other relevant metrics. Waste collection companies access this data through applications that display detailed information, allowing employees to track the status of all DUWTS containers across the city. However, the system only presents data for containers connected to the system, not comprehensively covering all waste management needs. For example, in one city, only eight container sites serve 800 residents, whereas 4,000 sites would be required to fully cover 40,000 residents. The high cost of the technology (nearly one million Polish zloty per site), as indicated by the city's mayor, makes broader implementation infeasible.

Despite the small scale, DUWTS promotes the narrative that data-driven insights should enable waste disposal companies to shift from traditional fixed schedules to performance-driven contracts. The introduction of dynamic waste collection should allow firms to adjust their schedules dynamically, aligning with actual waste production patterns. Arguments for dynamic waste collection suggest significant cost savings, enhanced efficiency through strategic planning for emptying, reduced environmental impact by saving vehicle fuel, and lower CO2 emissions. Theoretically, access to up-to-date data facilitates optimization of garbage truck routes, reducing unnecessary trips to partially filled containers. This approach is supported by literature: 'By leveraging artificial intelligence, municipalities can reduce costs, improve safety, and reduce environmental impacts associated with waste management.' (Frang et al., 2023).

This method of data reflectivity in the DUWTS waste disposal app supports the narrative of ‘smart’ waste management technologies, creating a futuristic vision of optimized operational strategies.

However, in practice, dynamic waste collection in the context of DUWTS faces significant technical, financial, and logistical barriers, making full implementation infeasible. Despite the theoretical potential, waste management practices still largely rely on traditional collection schedules. Waste collection companies, even with access to DUWTS app data, continue to follow pre-set plans, not fully utilizing the opportunities for dynamic waste collection. As a city official explains, schedules remain unchanged even when data from the app is available. The ideal scenario of dynamic waste management remains theoretical, limited by its implementation on selected estates only. Dynamic waste collection faces practical challenges, and employees from waste disposal companies confirm that traditional schedules are still followed.

The analysis of the second mirror reveals how critical accurate data reflection is for waste collection companies and highlights the broader implications of such technological integrations in urban waste management systems. Data reflectivity and accuracy do not necessarily lead to optimization. Infeasible dynamic waste collection demonstrates that the technology of (un)knowing creates illusions of potential possibilities. The second mirror and its kaleidoscopic reflections distort reality to create illusions of future possibilities for dynamic waste collection, obscuring or revealing complex relationships. Broader implications show that the technology of (un)knowing does not optimize but rather increases the workload for municipal employees, who lack the time and resources to fully engage with the system.

The official narrative often overlooks the practical limitations in implementing DUWTS on a larger scale, presenting an illusion of future possibilities. Offenhuber (2017:46) reveals that the greatest interest in dynamic waste collection lies with companies providing such technologies, which gives them power in contract negotiations. The promotion of dynamic waste collection through DUWTS app serves commercial interests rather than the public good. The data view in the application designed for waste disposal companies is tailored to specific interests, not neutral efficiency.

Envisioning a city-wide implementation of DUWTS fosters ambitious plans for the future of waste management. However, the vision of fully optimized waste management remains impractical, limited by high costs and logistical challenges. The official narrative about DUWTS often overlooks these practical limitations, promoting an idealized future. This raises questions about the neutrality of the narrative and whether it serves commercial or political

interests rather than the public good. The DUWTS system and its second mirror of data reflectivity reveal significant insights into how data accuracy and its presentation influence waste management practices. Understanding the socio-technological consequences of such systems is crucial in ensuring that their implementation genuinely benefits society and does not merely serve commercial interests.

Ceiling mirror: Data reflection to residents

The third mirror, the ceiling mirror, of data reflectivity in the DUWTS system illustrates how residents' waste data are mirrored in the app designed for their use. Residents can create an account through an HTML page or download the mobile app on their Android or iOS devices. They can also access the HTML application on a Windows computer. The primary infrastructure for this stage of data reflectivity is the residents' private smartphones. The data journey begins in the central system of the private tech company and concludes in the residents' apps. The DUWTS mobile app, designed for residents, is seen by the company's employees as "the final piece of the system for the most crucial player in this puzzle, the resident"

To further illustrate the functioning of this app, consider the "Ceiling Mirror" metaphor, which depicts how data transmitted from the DUWTS Central System to residents can be distorted, creating an illusion of inverted space. To understand this distortion, I will first present the types of data shown by the application and how they are displayed.

The app's features reflect data collected in the central DUWTS system, presenting it in a "very streamlined" manner with only the "basic information that essentially suffices for the user," as stated by a private-tech company worker. Although residents do not directly observe the journey of their data, they can access specific information through a dedicated app, which updates each time waste is disposed of in DUWTS containers, creating a precise history of the user's actions. Residents can monitor their data about the type (plastic, bio, paper, glass) and quantity of waste, capturing these details in individual app accounts. This real-time information enables accurate tracking of their individual waste management activities. "I have the opportunity to check my segregation, how many kilograms I have disposed of, and how it is represented percentage-wise," shares a resident, adding that the app also shows cumulative amounts of waste disposed, categorized by different fractions and periods. The data transmitted from the system is reflected in the app, creating a digital twin of the user. This virtual counterpart, based on precise data collection (Korenhof et al., 2023), represents real-time digital depictions of waste behaviors.

Residents can view personal statistics and metrics about the waste they generate and the recycling levels they achieve. The app presents this data within the context of larger datasets,

enabling users to assess whether their waste segregation practices align with EU recycling standards. By comparing personal results with anonymous statistics from other households, the app provides insights into personal achievements in waste segregation and allows evaluation relative to their neighborhood, municipality, and even the country. Additionally, the app transmits the results of sporadic inspections, displaying photos of waste bags taken by municipal employees and identified using QR codes. Residents receive notifications about these inspections, including thanks for correct segregation or warnings for errors, and this information is automatically available via the app.

The official aim of the app, according to the technology company, is to educate residents about the amount of municipal waste they generate and to encourage proper waste segregation practices. Municipal employees echo this sentiment, emphasizing that the technology is designed to teach residents how to properly segregate waste. The visibility of data in the residents' app, along with information about inspections, raises awareness about dataveillance, informing residents that building administration, municipality workers, and other units involved in waste management can access individual waste data. This strategy reinforces residents' responsibility for correct waste segregation. "Through comparison and competition, we aim to motivate residents to better segregate waste," explains a company employee, referring to the app's feature that allows residents to compare their waste management practices against broader datasets and EU recycling standards. Overall, this strategy of data reflection shapes a "quantifiable and quantified" human (Carlo Ratti, in: Offenhuber 2017, VII).

The most controversial feature of the app is the suggested fee for waste, calculated using the pay-as-you-throw (PAYT) method. PAYT is a system where residents pay based on the amount of waste they generate rather than a fixed rate for all households. The fee is proportional to the waste produced – the more waste, the higher the fee. However, this method is not recognized by Polish legislation. A municipal employee explains that the idea of implementing PAYT was rejected long ago because it would lead to illegal waste dumping in forests. Despite knowing that PAYT won't be implemented in Poland, the company responsible for the app included this feature to demonstrate the potential savings residents could achieve with DUWTS technology should PAYT ever be legally adopted.

This data reflection in the app is an effort to promote alternative system solutions that justify the existence of technology like DUWTS. However, it does not present actual data on real systems. The app shows the hypothetical benefits of implementing PAYT, aiming to illustrate the potential transition to this method. The suggested PAYT fee displayed in the app is misleading since it is not the actual amount residents have to pay. As a municipal employee

states, "We have requested the company to remove this feature from the app because residents call us demanding explanations for why the payment amount in the app differs (usually lower) from the flat fee they pay to the municipality for waste disposal, which is 33 PLN per person in a household." This example shows how some of the data displayed in the app is significantly misaligned with reality.

The idea of inverted space in the ceiling mirror of data reflectivity pertains to a paradigm shift in waste management responsibility. Traditionally, in multi-residential areas in Poland, waste management is a collective responsibility with shared fees. However, the application reverses this reality to shift responsibility. DUWTS introduces a new model that emphasizes individual liability through personalized waste management app. This shift transforms the dynamics of responsabilisation, making each resident liability for their waste generation and segregation. The "pay-as-you-throw" method, embodied in the application, mirrors this inversion by linking waste fees directly to the quantity and type of waste each individual disposes of. This method creates an illusion of fairness, shifting the collective responsibility for waste to the individual level.

This delegation of waste management responsibility to individual households by the private company responsible for DUWTS embodies what scholars term 'Technologies of (Un)Knowing' (Alexander, O'Hare, 2020). This shift is more than a mere administrative transfer; it serves as a strategy that conceals the deeper, systemic complexities of waste management across various sectors. It primarily focuses attention on the final stages of a product's lifecycle, often overshadowing its inception, design, production, distribution, and usage. This transition highlights the need to critically analyze the technologies and strategies employed in waste management and their broader impact on society.

This data-based individualization in the context of waste management, facilitated by DUWTS, represents a significant socio-technological shift. The advanced data collection and processing via the residents' app are used to self-evaluate individual waste management behaviors, shifting the responsibility for proper waste segregation onto the residents. This type of data reflectivity in the residents' app supports a narrative that locates the source of the problem within the individual, as if the resident alone is responsible for waste. Such a narrative obscures the responsibilities of public authorities and packaging producers, making it harder to identify other sources of the problem and alternative solutions.

Reflecting on the socio-technological consequences of this data reflectivity in the residents' app, one can conclude that data-based individualization aligns with the concept of the "technology of (un)knowing." The data-driven app generates an illusion of agency and control

over the amount of waste produced by residents, obscuring broader systemic issues. The ceiling mirror and its distorted reflections are strategies of technologies of (un)knowing, hiding the fact that it is not the residents who influence the effectiveness of the recycling process, but the packaging producers. The data shown in the app distort the real environmental impact, attributing more weight to individual actions than to systemic issues in waste production and management. They deflect attention from the greater waste produced by industrial, mining, and construction sectors, emphasizing individual citizens' responsibility for the waste crisis.

What happens to waste beyond the DUWTS infrastructure remains opaque (Offenhuber, 2017). Residents do not learn how much of their waste is actually recycled. The nature of data presentation in the app is selective and created for specific purposes. The app shows residents how much waste they are disposing of but does not show how much of it will actually be recycled. For example, similar to the proposed PAYT method, the app does not inform residents how many of the projected kilograms of waste they dispose of are suitable or unsuitable for recycling due to poor packaging quality. Presenting such information would shift the responsibility for waste towards the producers, which is not the goal of the residents' app. This selective presentation of data serves to create an illusion of individual control and responsibility, obscuring larger systemic issues and the role of producers in the waste management process.

Final reflections on data reflectivity in the DUWTS

In conclusion, this article argues that the Digital Urban Waste Tracking System (DUWTS) is an example of both a data-driven technological solution managed through surveillance and a classic 'technology of (un)knowing'. It posits that Smart Waste Management Technologies might conceal the true complexities of waste management because the process of 'data reflectivity' and the oversight thereof ('dataveillance') unfairly allocate waste responsibilities. While systems like DUWTS provide detailed data on recycling, they simultaneously risk reinforcing existing waste management issues, presenting these data-centric and algorithmic technologies as contemporary strategies that may unwittingly perpetuate the challenges they aim to resolve.

Systems like DUWTS, supplied to municipalities by private companies, merge these two spheres (public and private), raising significant questions about transparency and accountability, especially in the context of access to public information. They distort reality for four different purposes:

- creating an illusion of supervision and order (technology company)
- creating an illusion of control over recycling levels (municipalities)

- creating an illusion of future, futuristic visions of possibilities (waste collection companies)
- creating an illusion of agency over the amount of waste generated by oneself (citizen)

Technologies like DUWTS are often discussed in the context of the ‘smart city’ concept. Representatives of the company behind DUWTS claim, "We have gone a step further, in fact, several steps further, by designing a completely different, more modern system that fits the times we live in". DUWTS presents itself as a modern solution in urban waste management. While the underlying issues remain unaddressed, municipalities may receive accolades for merely using DUWTS, which unreflectively creates their image as a smart city.

In summary, DUWTS, while marking a significant technological advancement in urban waste management, embodies the dual aspects of technological progress – the promise of increased efficiency and control juxtaposed with challenges regarding masking real issues, such as the lack of systemic solutions like Extended Producer Responsibility. This duality highlights the need for a balanced approach that leverages the advantages of data-driven solutions while carefully navigating the ethical, social, and practical complexities inherent in such technological systems.

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Ethics Approval

The research project description, including ethical considerations, data management plan, and consent forms, is available at the Social Data Repository: <https://doi.org/10.60894/ANHJNA>.

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